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Preprocessing of SM Data: Improved Photometry

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1. Introduction

In NDAC/LO/011, a quasi-ML estimator was proposed for the transit time (τ). The estimation of the photometric SM signal parameters (a , b) was however treated rather superficially, and the method described is probably far from optimal. In view of the importance to get star colours also for the main mission, the present note indicates some possibilities for improving the photometric accuracy.

2. Basic Model

The SM signal model (for the transit of a single star) is

$$E(N_k^*) = \left[b + a S[(t_k - \tau)\dot{u}] \right] \Delta t^* \quad (1)$$

where b and a are the background and stellar intensities in Hz and S the known response function of the slit system. Assume that we have an estimate $\hat{\tau}$ of the transit time and define

$$S_k = S[(t_k - \hat{\tau})\dot{u}], \quad B = b \Delta t^*, \quad A = a \Delta t^* \quad (2)$$

so that the model can be written more concisely

$$E(N_k^*) = B + A S_k \quad (3)$$

The problem can be formulated as follows: Given a count record $\{N_k^*\}$ (where some samples may be missing) and a corresponding sequence $\{S_k\}$, estimate A and B with the assumption that the observed counts follow the Poisson distribution with expectation (3). As a second step of the problem, the estimation should be robust, i.e. relatively insensitive to deviations from the ideal model (3) due to other stars, spurious high counts, etc.

3. Maximum Likelihood (ML) Estimate

The (logarithmic) likelihood function is

$$\begin{aligned} \ell_o(a, b) &= \ln \left[\prod_k \frac{(B + AS_k)^{N_k^*}}{N_k^*!} \exp(-B - AS_k) \right] = \\ &= \text{const} + \sum_k N_k^* \ln(B + AS_k) - B \sum_k 1 - A \sum_k S_k \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

so that the likelihood equations $\partial \ell_o / \partial A = \partial \ell_o / \partial B = 0$ become

$$\sum_k \frac{S_k N_k^*}{\hat{B} + \hat{A} S_k} - \sum_k S_k = 0 \quad (5a)$$

$$\sum_k \frac{N_k^*}{\hat{B} + \hat{A} S_k} - \sum_k 1 = 0 \quad (5b)$$

with $\hat{A}$, $\hat{B}$ denoting the ML estimates. These are non-linear equations to be solved rapidly and accurately if the method should be of any use in the real processing. One possible solution method would be as follows. Multiply (5a) by $\langle S \rangle = \sum_k S_k / \sum_k 1$, take the difference and introduce $\hat{q} = \hat{A} / \hat{B}$. This gives a single non-linear equation for the flux ratio,

$$\sum_k \frac{S_k - \langle S \rangle}{1 + \hat{q} S_k} N_k^* = 0 \quad (6)$$

which can be solved by Newton-Raphson iteration:

$$\Delta q = \frac{\sum_k \frac{S_k - \langle S \rangle}{1 + q S_k} N_k^*}{\sum_k \frac{S_k}{1 + q S_k} \frac{S_k - \langle S \rangle}{1 + q S_k} N_k^*} ; \quad q := q + \Delta q \quad (7)$$

On the other hand, multiplying (5a) and (5b) by $\hat{A}$ and $\hat{B}$, respectively, and adding, we find

$$\hat{A} \sum_k S_k + \hat{B} \sum_k 1 = \sum_k N_k^* \quad (8)$$

from which

$$\hat{B} = \frac{\sum_k N_k^*}{\sum_k (1 + \hat{q} S_k)} \quad (9)$$

Finally, $\hat{A} = \hat{q}\hat{B}$. Some trial experiments indicated that (7) usually converges in two or three iterations, provided a reasonable starting approximation is given. This could be the unweighted least-squares estimate

$$q = \frac{\sum_k (S_k - \langle S \rangle) N_k^*}{\sum_k [\langle S^2 \rangle - \langle S \rangle S_k] N_k^*} \quad (10)$$

The accuracy of the ML estimates is obtained as the CR bound

$$\text{Cov} \begin{pmatrix} \hat{B} \\ \hat{A} \end{pmatrix} \geq \left[\sum_k \begin{pmatrix} 1 & S_k \\ S_k & S_k^2 \end{pmatrix} \frac{1}{B + AS_k} \right]^{-1} \quad (11)$$

Introducing the moments

$$m_n = \sum_k \frac{(q S_k)^n}{1 + q S_k} \quad (12)$$

we find in particular

$$\sigma_{\hat{A}}^2 = \frac{m_0}{m_0 m_2 - m_1^2} q^2 B, \quad \sigma_{\hat{B}}^2 = \frac{m_2}{m_0 m_2 - m_1^2} B \quad (13)$$

4. Quasi-Linear Estimates

We shall now attempt to get alternative estimates as linear combinations of the counts,

$$\hat{A} = \sum_k \alpha_k N_k^*, \quad \hat{B} = \sum_k \beta_k N_k^* \quad (14)$$

in which the coefficients α_k, β_k depend only weakly on the flux ratio $q = A/B$. More precisely, we require

(i) that $\alpha_k(q), \beta_k(q)$ give unbiased estimates for $q \neq q_{\text{true}}$;

(ii) that the estimates are minimum variance for $q = q_{\text{true}}$.

The first condition yields the equations

$$E(\hat{A}) \equiv \sum_k \alpha_k (B + AS_k) \equiv B \sum_k \alpha_k + A \sum_k S_k \alpha_k = A \quad (15a)$$

$$E(\hat{B}) \equiv \sum_k \beta_k (B + AS_k) \equiv B \sum_k \beta_k + A \sum_k S_k \beta_k = B \quad (15b)$$

which are most easily satisfied by requiring

$$\sum_k \beta_k = 1, \quad \sum_k S_k \beta_k = 0 \quad (16a)$$

$$\sum_k \alpha_k = 0, \quad \sum_k S_k \alpha_k = 1 \quad (16b)$$

Using the Poisson property,

$$\text{var}(N_k^*) = E(N_k^*) \quad (17)$$

and the statistical independence of the counts, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \text{var}(\hat{B}) &= \text{var}(\sum_k \beta_k N_k^*) \\ &= \sum_k \beta_k^2 \text{var}(N_k^*) \\ &= \sum_k \beta_k^2 (B + AS_k) \\ &= B \sum_k \beta_k^2 + A \sum_k S_k \beta_k^2 \end{aligned} \quad (18a)$$

and similarly

$$\text{var}(\hat{A}) = B \sum_k \alpha_k^2 + A \sum_k S_k \alpha_k^2 \quad (18b)$$

Minimizing (18a) and (18b) subject to (16a)-(16b) yields

$$\beta_k = \frac{1}{m_0 m_2 - m_1^2} \frac{-m_1 q S_k + m_2}{1 + q S_k} \quad (19a)$$

$$\alpha_k = \frac{q}{m_0 m_2 - m_1^2} \frac{m_0 q S_k - m_1}{1 + q S_k} \quad (19b)$$

where $q = q_{\text{true}}$. Note however that (16a)-(16b) are satisfied with any q -value, as required by (i). In the case when $q = q_{\text{true}}$, we find that the variances (18a)-(18b) become equal to the CR limits (13). But even with q -values significantly deviating from q_{true} the variances are only slightly above the CR values (cf Table 1).

Because of this there is hardly any need to iterate the solution and using an improved q -value to recompute the coefficients β_k, α_k ; hence the designation quasi-linear.

Table 1. $\text{var}(\hat{A})$ according to (18b) and (19b), versus the q -value used to compute the coefficients α_k . The response values used in this example are $\{s_k\} = \{.70, .65, .37, .16, .06, .03, .01, 13 \times 0\}$.

A = 1, B = 1 ($q_{\text{true}} = 1$)		A = 5, B = 1 ($q_{\text{true}} = 5$)		A = 25, B = 1 ($q_{\text{true}} = 25$)	
q	var($\hat{A}$)	q	var($\hat{A}$)	q	var($\hat{A}$)
0.25	1.73557	1.0	4.05692	10	14.6063
0.50	1.73052	2.0	4.00127	16	14.5125
0.75	1.72802	3.0	3.97624	19	14.4946
1.00	1.72730	4.0	3.96571	22	14.4862
1.25	1.72788	5.0	3.96302	25	14.4839
1.50	1.72942	6.0	3.96495	28	14.4857
1.75	1.73167	7.0	3.96975	31	14.4902
2.00	1.73446	10.0	3.99293	37	14.5043
3.00	1.74895	15.0	4.04120	70	14.6116

5. Conclusion

The ML equations for estimating the photometric SM signal parameters A and B (or a and b) are non-linear and require iteration for a strict solution. The quasi-linear estimates, on the other hand, will almost reach the CR limit without iteration, provided that a reasonable value for the flux ratio ($q = A/B$) is known a priori (or from the position filter). In this case the quasi-linear filter should be computationally much more efficient, comprising the following steps:

(i) input: $\{N_k^*\}$, $\{S_k\}$, q

(ii) compute m_0 , m_1 , m_2 according to (12) and

$$\mu_0 = \sum_k \frac{1}{1 + qS_k} N_k^*, \quad \mu_1 = \sum_k \frac{qS_k}{1 + qS_k} N_k^* = \sum_k N_k^* - \mu_0 \quad (20)$$

(iii) the estimates and their estimated variances are obtained as

$$\hat{B} = \Delta^{-1} (m_2 \mu_0 - m_1 \mu_1), \quad \hat{A} = \Delta^{-1} (m_0 \mu_1 - m_1 \mu_0) \quad (21)$$

$$\sigma_{\hat{B}}^2 = \Delta^{-1} m_2 \hat{B}, \quad \sigma_{\hat{A}}^2 = \Delta^{-1} m_0 \hat{A}^2 / \hat{B} \quad (22)$$

with

$$\Delta = m_0 m_2 - m_1^2 \quad (23)$$